

Impact of Joint Improvised Material on Creative-Thinking Originality among Mixed-Ability Upper Basic Science Students in Makurdi Metropolis

Ayua, Geoffrey Aondolumun¹
ayuageoffrey@gmail.com

Ikyernum, Gabriel Sesugh²
sesughgabriel05@gmail.com

Gwamna, Mariana Nenadi³
nenadi@gmail.com

Akaasah, Yvonne Yuadoo⁴
yakaasah@gmail.com

¹Department of Science & Mathematics Education, Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria

⁴Department of Chemistry, Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria

³Department of Special Needs Education, Kaduna State College of Education, Gidan Waya, Nigeria

²Department of Agricultural Technology, School of Applied Sciences, Federal Polytechnic, Ile-Oluji/Okeigbo, Ondo State, Nigeria

Abstract

Impact of Joint Improvised Material on Creative-Thinking Originality among mixed ability upper Basic Science students in Makurdi was studied using pre-test post-test quasi-experimental-control group research design. The study was guided by two research questions and corresponding hypotheses. The study's population was made up of 1337 (680 male and 657 female) Upper Basic II government secondary school in Makurdi metropolis. Fifty-two students (22 male & 30 female) constitute the sample size of the study. Hence, this was arrived at using multi stage sampling technique. Torrance Test of Creative Thinking with a reliability coefficient of 0.82 determined by a test-retest method was used for data collection. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and two-way Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). Findings showed no significant difference in creative-thinking originality among mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Joint Improvised Material and those taught using Teacher Improvised Material, $F_{(2, 45)} = 1.095$; $p = .343 > .05$. Although, there existed a significant difference in creative-thinking originality in favour of those taught using Joint Improvised Material, $F_{(1, 45)} = 61.438$; $p = .000 < .05$, no significant difference existed in the students' creative-thinking originality based on gender, $F_{(2, 45)} = 1.564$; $p = .220 > .05$. Therefore, it was concluded that, enhancing creative-thinking originality among students with different abilities can be achieved without any gender discrepancy by actively involving learners in the improvisation of instructional materials. Thus, Joint Improvisation Approach was recommended for teaching Basic Science in basic schools.

Keywords: Joint Improvised Material (JIM), Teacher Improvised Material (TIM), Creative-Thinking Originality, Mixed Ability and Gender

Introduction

In today's rapidly changing world, where innovation and adaptability are paramount, the role of creativity in education has never been more crucial. Education no longer solely revolves around the acquisition of knowledge; it must also empower students with the creative thinking skills necessary to navigate the complexities of the 21st century (Handayani et al., 2022; Nazhifah et al., 2023). To prepare learners for the ever-evolving challenges, fostering creativity within educational institutions has become imperative. Creativity not only equips students with the ability to adapt and innovate but also empowers them to think creatively and engage with the world in meaningful ways. Creativity in education sparks curiosity, fosters creative thinking, and nurtures problem-solving abilities, equipping students with the tools to confront novel challenges and envision innovative solutions (Akhshabi & Dortaj, 2022; Setyaningsih & Kustiana, 2023). This shift towards a more creative educational

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paradigm not only enhances individual growth but also cultivates a generation better prepared to shape a dynamic and ever-evolving global landscape of the current age.

Creativity in science education is contemporarily indispensable. Science is not merely about memorizing facts and formulas; it's about exploration, discovery, and innovation (Handayani et al., 2022; Tanjung et al., 2023). Fostering creativity in science education empowers students to ask questions, experiment, and think creatively, preparing them to tackle complex real-world challenges (Oliveira et al., 2021; Fatmawati et al., 2022). In a rapidly advancing scientific landscape, where interdisciplinary collaboration and novel solutions are essential, nurturing creativity ensures that the next generation of scientists can adapt, contribute, and lead in pushing the boundaries of knowledge and addressing pressing global issues through creativity.

Creativity is the human capacity to discover fresh solutions to challenges by leveraging our existing knowledge. It emerges from our awareness of an imbalance in the environment, leading to productive actions that defy established thought patterns and conventions, ultimately giving rise to novel outcomes, whether tangible objects or abstract mental and emotional constructs. (Apaydin, 2023; Balci et al., 2023). Creativity thus implies the act of turning new and imaginative ideas into reality. In our age, where information is developing and changing very rapidly, societies need individuals who are proactive, thinking creative, problem-solving, and constantly improving themselves in order to adapt to this change and development (Apaydin, 2023; Smare & Elfatih 2023). Therefore, this infers that in order to confirm a sustainable development, implementing innovative strategies aimed at nurturing creativity skills, particularly fostering creative thinking among learners becomes pertinent.

Creative thinking refers to the ability to generate diverse and numerous responses to a particular issue that increases the likely output of creative ideas (Aldossari, 2021; He & Wong, 2021; Tanjung et al., 2023). According to Ayua et al., (2023) Creative thinking is one's cognitive process to generate effective ideas in solving problems under certain aims and conditions. It is a positive action in stimulating brain function that can create a proper learning style. In whichever way one views creative thinking, it is generally considered as a process of thinking based on what has been or formed from the knowledge relationship with reality, which results in creating something new. Creative thinking skills are highly prized by nations, researchers, educators, and workplaces, motivating them to adopt inventive teaching strategies to bolster creativity. In alignment with this, the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) in her national policy on education emphasizes the exposure of learners to Basic Science concepts to develop skills and knowledge necessary for meeting contemporary societal needs. This approach aims to cultivate the skills and knowledge essential for addressing the evolving demands of modern society. A fundamental goal of Basic Science education is to promote the development of creative thinking skills in learners, which is facilitated through the use of effective teaching and learning materials.

However, it is worth highlighting that research consistently emphasizes the insufficient access to instructional materials in Nigerian primary and secondary schools, as pointed out by the National Teachers' Institute (NTI) as cited in the work of Ikyernum et al., 2022. Frequently, the existing materials are insufficient or outdated, compelling educators to take on the task of implementing hands-on teaching strategies at the fundamental education level. In their role as facilitators of the teaching and learning process, teachers find themselves compelled to improvise and adapt to the tenets of Basic Science teaching as outlined by FRN (2013), ensuring effective classroom instruction even when confronted with a dearth of suitable teaching and learning resources.

Improvisation refers to selection or provision for something not readily available. It is the process by which educational materials can be designed and developed using locally available materials to meet specific instructional needs (Ayua et al., 2022; Ikyernum et al., 2022). To impart meaningful science education, especially at the basic school level, it is crucial to have sufficient teaching and learning materials. Unfortunately, Ayua (2021) reported that education is facing challenges due to inadequate funding and a growing student population, leading to difficulties in acquiring resources for practical demonstrations. Consequently, there arises a need to utilize local materials and improvise in the teaching and learning of Basic Science. This approach is essential as it aligns with Bruner's (1966) emphasis on learning through hands-on experiences and creative thinking, aided by the use of concrete objects. By incorporating these methods, Basic Science can become more engaging and relevant to students. Improvisation according to Ayua (2021) could be by substitution, modification and construction either solely by the teacher (Teacher Improvised Material) or by the combined efforts of the teacher and learners (Joint Improvised Material).

Teacher Improvised Material (TIM) refers to teaching aid(s) made by the teacher alone and brought to the classroom for Basic Science teaching. TIM is an improvisation approach that is teacher-based because learners are not involved in the process of producing the improvised instructional material(s) (Ikyernum et al., 2022). Joint Improvised Material (JIM) on the

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other hand refers to teaching aids that are collaboratively produced by both the teacher and the learners for the purpose of Basic Science teaching and learning (Ikyernum et al., 2022). This approach emphasizes the active involvement of both the teacher and the students in creating these materials. By adopting a joint improvisation method, students gain essential knowledge about the subject matter and are encouraged to think creatively even before the actual lessons take place. This process fosters a more engaging and interactive learning environment, allowing students to actively participate in their education and take ownership of their learning experiences. This paper will center its attention on these two improvisation techniques, with the objective of assessing their impact on creative-thinking originality of mixed-ability upper Basic Science learners.

In the realm of science education, creativity takes center stage as an indispensable catalyst for innovation and progress. The process of improvisation, fueled by creative thinking, plays a pivotal role in fostering deeper comprehension and engagement among learners. It empowers students to explore unfamiliar territories, experiment with new ideas, and adapt to evolving scientific challenges (Ikyernum et al., 2022). The integration of improvisation into the teaching and learning process is increasingly acknowledged as a means to cultivate and amplify creative thinking among students (Navarro, 2018). This approach not only equips students with essential skills for societal achievement but also serves as a catalyst for economic progress in our technology-driven 21st-century global landscape.

Consequently, it becomes crucial to prioritize the development of creative thinking and improvisation within educational settings, enabling students to thrive amid the dynamic and multifaceted challenges of our ever-evolving world. Creative thinking comprises five sub domains of fluency, originality, elaboration, resistance to premature closure and abstractness of tittles (Tehemba et al., 2023). However, this paper focuses on creative-thinking originality.

Creative-thinking originality is the ability to remove the phrase, idea, or an idea to solve a problem or make a combination of parts or elements are unusual, unique, novel that had not occurred to anyone else or the ability to produce a definition of rare and original of ideas, ability to generate original ideas, techniques or design of the expression that is rarely encountered (Trisnayanti et al., 2020; Chua et al., 2020). Creative-thinking originality breeds creativity. Originality frequently stands out as one of the most commonly acknowledged aspects of creativity (Fontenot as cited in Terhemba et al., 2023). Originality can be seen in something as small as a unique idea produced in everyday life to something as big as unconventional scientific progress (Terhemba et al., 2023). Creative-thinking originality holds significant importance in the realm of creativity, as it plays a pivotal role in nurturing valuable ideas. These ideas, in turn, provide individuals with the essential competences necessary to excel in contemporary societies fueled by creativity. Empirically, Empirically, Özgenel et al., (2019) and Chua et al., (2020) in their respective studies on creative thinking found that there was a significant increase in creative thinking originality after students were exposed to the enriched trainings to foster creative thinking skills. Likewise, Ng and Lee (2019) in their study “assessment of creative thinking of Hong Kong undergraduate students using the Torrance Tests of Creative Thinking” found that learners ‘creative-thinking originality scores were well above average. In contrast, Trisnayanti et al., (2020) found no significant improvement in the creative thinking originality scores of learners as originality scores had the lowest percentage value of all the five sub domains of creative thinking. In the same vein, Fatmawati et al., (2022) reported no significant treatment effect on creative-thinking originality scores after learners were exposed to Creative Problem-Solving based Learning. Though the studies assessed the creative-thinking originality of learners, they however were not concerned with creative-thinking originality as an aspect of creative thinking in relation to improvisation across mixed ability learners.

Ability in this research refers to the different educational performance levels of students in Basic Science, which can be categorized as high, average, or low based on their past academic scores. Maikano as cited in Ikyernum, et al., (2022) suggests that ability grouping is determined by educators' assessments of students' abilities. When assigning students to different tracks, their prior test scores or performance measures from previous grades or schools are considered to determine their ability levels. Students' ability levels for the study were guided by Benue State Ministry of Education – BSME (2021) and Benue State Examinations Board – BSEB (2019) grading system for basic schools. Based on the grading system, High Ability Level (A = 75-100% and B = 65-74%), Average Ability Level (C = 55-64% and D = 45-54%) and Low Ability Level (E = 40-44% and F = 0-39%). By using this grading system, the researchers were able to distinguish and group students based on their academic ability levels in Basic Science. Empirically, Ikyernum et al., (2022) in their study “Effect of teacher-learner improvised material on creative thinking among mixed ability upper Basic Science students in Makurdi metropolis” established that the level of creative thinking among mixed ability students was significantly enhanced without gender disparity as a result of learners' active involvement in the improvisation of instructional materials. However, Setyaningsih and Kustiana (2023) in their study “Analysis of Students' Creative Thinking Ability in Solving HOTS Problems Viewed from Numeration Ability” established that learners mathematical creative-thinking originality is dependent on their numerical abilities; as learners with average and low numerical abilities could not achieve creative-thinking originality in Solving HOTS Problems. These studies

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however were not concerned with creative-thinking originality in relation to improvisation and did not tell whether a difference existed in creative-thinking originality based on gender as a result of learners' involvement in improvisation of instructional materials.

Gender differences encompass the characteristics associated with being male or female, man or woman, boy or girl. Research by Danjuma (as cited in Ayua, 2021) indicates that these gender disparities have a worldwide impact, particularly in Africa, by hindering the equal participation of boys and girls in Science Education. Consequently, these gender-specific factors influence the teaching, learning, and creative thinking of students in Basic Science. Empirically, Ulger and Morsunbul (2017); Zhang et al., (2020), in their respective studies on differences in creative thinking found that a significant difference existed in creative thinking abilities between males and females in favour of females. However, Ayua and Agbidye (2020); He and Wong (2021); Ayua et al (2022) and Terhemba et al. (2023) found no significant difference between boys and girls in the level of entrepreneurial creativity, divergent thinking and problem-solving skills, creative thinking, and creative-thinking originality respectively. However, none of the studies were concerned with creative-thinking originality as an aspect of creative thinking in relation to improvisation. That is why impact of joint improvisation on creative-thinking originality among mixed ability upper Basic Science students is pertinent.

In the contemporary era, characterized by remarkable scientific and technological advancements, the educational landscape has witnessed profound transformations. These shifts, attributed to the knowledge revolution and rapid technological progress, underscore the paramount importance of nurturing creativity skills in an ever-evolving world. To effectively navigate this dynamic environment, educational leaders must realign their strategies to align with these transformative trends. This is particularly relevant for upper Basic Science students, who must cultivate creative-thinking abilities for both academic and professional success. One promising avenue for fostering creativity is through improvisation. By encouraging spontaneous thinking, imaginative problem-solving, adaptability, and unconventional approaches, improvisation holds the potential to ignite creativity. However, there is a need to explore in-depth the extent to which improvisation techniques can effectively enhance the creative-thinking originality among upper Basic Science students. This study aims to investigate the impact of implementing improvisation techniques on learners' creative-thinking originality in the context of Basic Science education. By examining the practical application of improvisation in the classroom, this research seeks to provide insights into its viability as a means to nurture creative-thinking originality in students. This investigation addresses the pressing demand to cultivate creativity skills in today's educational landscape and offers valuable insights into how improvisation can serve as a catalyst for enhancing creative-thinking originality among 21st-century learners.

Objectives of the Study

Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. To determine the mean creative-thinking originality scores of students taught Basic Science using Joint Improvised Material and those taught using Teacher Improvised Material
2. To find out the mean creative-thinking originality scores among mixed ability male and female students taught Basic Science using Joint Improvised Material.

Research Questions

1. What is the mean difference in creative-thinking originality scores among mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Joint Improvised Material and those taught using Teacher Improvised Material?
2. What is the mean difference in creative-thinking originality scores among mixed ability male and female students taught Basic Science using Joint Improvised Material?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in mean creative-thinking originality scores among mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Joint Improvised Material and those taught using Teacher Improvised Material.
2. There is no significant difference in mean creative-thinking originality scores among mixed ability male and female students taught Basic Science using Joint Improvised Material.

Methodology

A pre-test post-test quasi-experimental-control group design was used for this study. After pre-test administration, the experimental group of an intact class of 1:24 was taught concept of work, energy and power with 5 lesson plans using demonstration method blended with Joint Improvised Materials (wooden toy car and wooden electric fan) constructed through active involvement of learners together with the teacher using procedures outlined in the lesson plans; while the control group

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was taught the same concept using same method blended with Teacher Improvised Materials. This treatment lasted for five weeks. Thereafter, the students in both groups were given post-test. Students mixed ability were based on previous term's performance grades (high = A/B; average = C/D; low = E/F). Fifty-two (22 male & 30 female) students constitute the sample size of the study. Hence, this was arrived at using multi stage sampling technique from the population of 1337 (680 males and 657 females) Upper Basic II students in all the 21 secondary schools (Teaching Service Board Makurdi, 2021) Torrance Test of Creative Thinking (TTCT-Figural B) was used for data collection. Section "A" collected students' biodata; while section 'B' had three activities each lasting for 10 minutes with the opportunity for multiple responses of ideas, to test students' creative-thinking originality in Basic Science. TTCT-Figural B was validated and trial-tested with a reliability coefficient of 0.82 determined by a test-retest method with Pearson Product Moment Correlation. Extraneous variables like group initial difference, group interaction effect and priming were controlled by homogeneity test, distant locations and impromptu tests respectively. Both pre-test and post-test were administered under standard examination conditions. The research questions were answered using mean and hypotheses were tested at 0.05 α -level using a two-way Analysis of covariance due to normality of the distribution, homogeneity of variance, randomness of selection, measurement based on interval scale and independence of samples.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean difference in creative-thinking originality scores among mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Joint Improvised Material and those taught using Teacher Improvised Material?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Creative-Thinking Originality Scores of Students Taught Using Joint Improvised Material and Teacher Improvised Material.

Ability Level	N	Group	Pre-TTCT		Post-TTCT		Mean Gain	Mean Gain difference
			$\bar{x}$	SD	$\bar{x}$	SD		
High	12	TIM	2.01	0.620	3.35	0.996	1.34	2.44
	10	JIM	2.27	0.726	6.05	1.202	3.78	
Average	8	TIM	2.35	1.078	3.11	0.806	0.76	1.97
	7	JIM	2.30	0.166	5.03	1.053	2.73	
Low	8	TIM	1.79	0.669	2.35	0.930	0.56	3.14
	7	JIM	1.84	0.207	5.54	1.398	3.70	
Cluster		TIM	2.05		2.94		0.89	2.52
		JIM	2.13		5.54		3.41	

Table 1 shows homogeneity in the pre-test mean scores among mixed ability between experimental and control group with cluster means of 2.13 and 2.05. The table also shows that creative-thinking originality mean scores among mixed ability in the experimental group were higher than those in the control group with cluster mean gain difference of 2.52.

Research Question 2

What is the mean difference in creative-thinking originality scores among mixed ability male and female students taught Basic Science using Joint Improvised Material?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Creative-Thinking Originality Scores of Male and Female Students Taught Using Joint Improvised Material

Ability Level	Gender	N	Pre-TTCT		Post-TTCT		Mean Gain	Mean Gain Difference
			$\bar{x}$	SD	$\bar{x}$	SD		
High	Male	7	2.38	0.701	4.80	1.184	2.42	0.72
	Female	3	1.87	0.548	3.57	1.657	1.70	
Average	Male	2	1.99	0.953	4.01	1.040	2.20	0.83
	Female	5	2.63	1.155	4.00	1.622	1.37	
Low	Male	2	2.00	0.000	4.00	2.160	1.80	

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	Female	5	1.75	0.566	3.78	2.257	2.03	0.23
Cluster	Male		2.12		4.27		2.15	
	Female		2.08		3.78		1.70	0.45

Table 2 shows homogeneity in the pre-test mean scores between male and female in the experimental group with cluster means of 2.12 and 2.08. Likewise, the table also shows that the creative-thinking originality mean scores in the post-test was higher than those in the pre-test in both male and female with cluster mean gains of 2.15 and 1.70 respectively

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant mean difference in creative-thinking originality scores among mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Joint Improvised Material and those taught using Teacher Improvised Material.

Table 3: Summary of Two-way ANCOVA Results of Creative-Thinking Originality Test Scores of Students Based on Improvisation Technique

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	98.200 ^a	6	16.367	12.054	.000	.616
Intercept	85.353	1	85.353	62.863	.000	.583
TTCT_pretest	1.035	1	1.035	.763	.387	.017
Ability_Level	5.792	2	2.896	2.133	.130	.087
Improvisation_Technique	83.418	1	83.418	61.438	.000	.577
Ability_Level * Improvisation_Technique	2.974	2	1.487	1.095	.343	.046
Error	61.100	45	1.358			
Total	1076.580	52				
Corrected Total	159.300	51				

a. R Squared = .616 (Adjusted R Squared = .565)

Table 3 shows no significant difference in the creative-thinking originality scores among mixed ability students taught Basic Science using TIM and those taught using JIM, $F_{(2, 45)} = 1.095$; $p = .343 > .05$. The null hypothesis was therefore not rejected. However, the result also showed that students' creative-thinking originality scores in the experimental group was better than those in the control group, $F_{(1, 45)} = 61.438$; $p = .000 < .05$. This implies that, although Joint Improvised Material (JIM) enhances creative-thinking originality, it is not dependent on students' academic abilities.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant mean difference in creative-thinking originality scores among mixed ability male and female students taught Basic Science using Joint Improvised Material

Table 4. Summary of Two-way ANCOVA Results of Creative-Thinking Originality Scores of Male and Female Students Taught Using Joint Improvised Material

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	28.549 ^a	6	4.758	1.638	.159	.179
Intercept	76.865	1	76.865	26.454	.000	.370
TTCT_pretest	.572	1	.572	.197	.659	.004
Ability_Level	4.641	2	2.321	.799	.456	.034
Gender	6.247	1	6.247	2.150	.150	.046
Ability_Level * Gender	9.091	2	4.546	1.564	.220	.065
Error	130.751	45	2.906			
Total	1076.580	52				
Corrected Total	159.300	51				

a. R Squared = .179 (Adjusted R Squared = .070)

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Table 4 showed no significant difference in the creative-thinking originality scores between male and female mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Teacher-Learner Improvised Material, $F_{(2, 45)} = 1.564$; $p = .220 > .05$. The null hypothesis was therefore not rejected. This implies that, Joint Improvised Material is gender unbiased; hence it enhanced creative-thinking originality in both male and female mixed ability Basic Science students.

Discussion of Findings

Concerning students' creative-thinking originality based on involving them in improvising instructional materials, it was found that significant difference existed in creative- thinking originality between students in the control and experimental groups in favour of those in the experimental group. However, among the ability levels there existed no significant difference in creative-thinking originality. Following field experience, the finding of this study is not odd because during the construction process, students were given ample opportunity to fully express their open-mindedness towards production of novel, unique and uncommon ideas and converting same into meaningful and scintillating materials or objects which thus entail creative-thinking originality. This finding is similar with Özgenel et al., (2019) who found that there was a significant increase in creative-thinking originality after students were exposed to the enriched training to foster creative thinking. The finding also agrees with that of Ng & Lee (2019) who established that learners' creative-thinking originality was well above average. However, the finding does not only contrast with, but is a potential solution to those of Trisnayanti et al., (2020) and Fatmawati et al., (2022) who found no significant improvement in the creative thinking originality after learners were exposed to creative thinking enhancement programmes. The indifference among mixed ability students in creative-thinking originality as found out, is similar to the finding of Ikyernum, et al. (2022) of no significant difference in creative thinking among varied ability students. However, the finding does not only differ slightly with, but is also a potential solution to the finding of Setyaningsih and Kustiana (2023) who found that learners mathematical creative-thinking originality is dependent on their numerical abilities; as leaners with average and low numerical abilities could not achieve creative-thinking originality in Solving HOTS Problems.

Regarding students' creative-thinking originality based on gender, it was discovered that no significant difference existed in creative-thinking originality between male and female mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Joint Improvised Material. Thus, involving students in the improvisation of instructional materials to enhance their creative-thinking originality is gender unbiased. This finding is similar to those of Ayua and Agbidye (2020); He and Wong (2021); Ayua et al., (2022) and Terhemba et al., (2023) who found no significant difference between boys and girls in the level of entrepreneurial creativity, divergent thinking and problem-solving skills, creative thinking, and creative-thinking originality respectively. This finding however does not only differ but also is solution to Ulger and Morsunbul (2017), Zhang et al., (2020) who found out that a significant difference existed between females and males upon creative thinking in favour of females.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that: Creative-thinking originality among varied ability students can be enhanced without gender discrepancy if learners are actively involved in the improvisation of instructional materials.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made to effectively implement this approach:

1. Joint Improvisation approach should be adopted in teaching Basic Science.
2. School administrators should encourage researchers to organize workshops on the use of Joint Improvisation.
3. Ministries of Education and teacher training institutions in Nigeria should ensure in-service training and retraining of teachers on Joint Improvisation.
4. School proprietors, heads and parents' teachers' association should materially/financially support Joint Improvisation in Basic Science.

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